

Code	Description	Examples
Include timeline references for bots	A short line to link bot comments in the main conversation timeline	<p>"a notification like 'a bot comment has occurred here' so the user can click to switch tabs." [P9]</p> <p>"GitHub interface could simply merge them into one: 'there were lots of bot comments here,' since one of the goals is also to remove the noise." [P9]</p>
Quoting bot comments on the main conversation	Bot quotation within the human comment	<p>"But maybe if you could do something more like a quote" [P30]</p> <p>"As you can put a snippet of code in the comment in GitHub, you can do the same for bots' outputs." [P27]</p>
Enhance newcomers bot message	Adjustments in the message the meta-bot shows to newcomers	<p>"reuse the icons of the bots a little bit and kind of show visually from which bot is the warning coming from" [P16]</p> <p>"Since it is a table, you can put the name in the second or first column instead of having it in the end." [P27]</p>
Move summary to the main conversation	Create a specific place for the meta-bot summary	<p>"like a side panel. Then, the summary can always be visible. And all the detailed information could be in the bot conversation" [P27]</p>
Interactive comments as opt-out feature	Add an interactive version of meta-bot summary as an opt-out feature	<p>"even if the person is new to the repository, maybe [she] is a contributor who is very used to contributing to other repositories. So then it's good that you can opt-out." [P30]</p>
Replace bots tab name	Replace the tab name for a name that does not imply a dialog between bots	<p>"But I'm not sure that it should be called conversation also, because it's more like history. I don't expect that the bots will have a discussion or conversation between them. For the bots it is just history." [P27]</p>
Filtering bot interactions	Option to filter out the interactions in the bots' timeline	<p>"if there are multiple comments from Reakit bot, for example, then I would like to see a thread only with chronological comments. Then, I can follow only this bot, and I don't need to go through it manually." [P16]</p>